

Synthesis and characterization of mixed ligand complexes of molybdenum(VI)

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Abstract : The mixed ligand complexes of molybdenum(VI) of the type, $[\text{MoO}_2(\text{acac})_2\text{L}]$ where L = morpholinomethyl urea (MMU), morpholinomethyl thiourea (MMTU), piperidinomethyl urea (PMU), piperidinomethyl thiourea (PMTU), pyrrolidinomethyl urea (PyMU) and pyrrolidinomethyl thiourea (PyMTU) have been prepared by the reaction of $[\text{MoO}_2(\text{acac})_2]$ with corresponding ligands in 1 : 1 molar ratio. The complexes have been characterized by various physico-chemical techniques such as elemental analysis, molar conductance, IR, electronic spectra, cyclic voltammetry in addition to TGA/DTA studies. Morpholinomethyl urea and related ligands behave as monodentate in the complexes coordinating to molybdenum through carbonyl oxygen or thiocarbonyl sulfur.

Keywords : Mixed ligand complexes, molybdenum(VI), substituted urea.

Complexes of molybdenum have been the subject of numerous recent studies because of their potential for application in homogeneous catalytic processes¹⁻³ and various metabolic processes⁴⁻⁸. The complexes of molybdenum are also studied as models for molybdenum containing enzymes⁹⁻¹¹.

It is well-known that the strong tendency to form very stable six membered chelate ring dominates the chemistry of β -diketonate ligands¹² and dioxobis(2,4-pentanedionato)molybdenum(VI) complex is known since long^{13,14}. This complex has been used to prepare numerous complexes of MoO_2^{2+} unit containing Schiff's base ligands^{15,16}. It is shown that for uninegative ligands (HL), complexes usually take the form $[\text{MoO}_2\text{L}_2$ or $\text{MoO}_2(\text{acac})\text{L}]$ and for dianionic ones (H_2L), complexes of the type $[\text{MoO}_2\text{LS}]$ (where S = solvent) have been reported¹⁷⁻¹⁹. The novel seven and eight coordinated *cis*- MoO_2^{VI} mononuclear complexes of the type, $\text{MoO}_2(\text{acac})_2\text{L}$ and $\text{MoO}_2(\text{acac})\text{L}_2$ have also been prepared by the reaction of $\text{MoO}_2(\text{acac})_2$ with various ligands such as 2-diphenylphosphinoyl-2'-hydroxy-1,1'-binaphthalene (Hbinappo), (1*S*)-2-diphenylphosphoryl)-1-methylethanol $\{\text{Ph}_2\text{P}(=\text{O})\text{CH}_2\text{CHMeOH}\}$ and (1*R*)-2-diphenylphosphoryl)-1-phenylethanol $\{\text{Ph}_2\text{P}(=\text{O})\text{CH}_2\text{CHPhOH}\}$ in different molar ratios²⁰⁻²². Besides this the complexes of morpholinomethyl urea and morpholinomethyl thiourea with some divalent transition metals viz. Co^{II} and Cu^{II}

have been studied in respect of their bonding, thermal and magnetic behaviour^{23,24}. The complexes of morpholinomethyl urea and related ligands with rare earth metals have also been reported²⁵⁻²⁷.

The present paper describes the synthesis and characterization of some mixed ligand complexes of molybdenum(VI) with morpholinomethyl urea and related ligands.

Results and discussion

The analytical and spectroscopic data (Tables 1 and 2) showed that all the complexes are mononuclear with general formula, $[\text{MoO}_2(\text{acac})_2\text{L}]$ where L = morpholinomethyl urea (MMU), morpholinomethyl thiourea (MMTU), piperidinomethyl urea (PMU), piperidinomethyl thiourea (PMTU), pyrrolidinomethyl urea (PyMU) and pyrrolidinomethyl thiourea (PyMTU). All complexes are coloured, stable in air and insoluble in common organic solvents like CHCl_3 , CCl_4 , CH_3OH , $\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{OH}$ etc. but soluble in DMF and DMSO.

Conductance measurements :

The molar conductance of these complexes in 10^{-3} M DMF solution is in the range of $38-52 \Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^2 \text{mol}^{-1}$ which is much lower than the value obtained for 1 : 1 electrolytes in this solvent indicating non-electrolytic nature of these complexes.

Table 1. Analytical and physical data of complexes

Sl. no.	Complex (Emp. formula)	Colour	Dec. temp. (°C)	Found (Calcd.)%					Molar conductivity ($\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$)
				Mo	C	H	N	S	
1.	MoO ₂ (acac) ₂ .MMU (MoC ₁₆ H ₂₇ N ₃ O ₈)	Light green	235	19.77 (19.92)	39.56 (39.61)	5.56 (5.53)	8.65 (8.62)	- (8.62)	49
2.	MoO ₂ (acac) ₂ .MMTU (MoC ₁₆ H ₂₇ N ₃ O ₇ S)	Dirty white	238	19.13 (19.22)	38.29 (38.34)	5.39 (5.34)	8.39 (8.32)	6.38 (6.43)	41
3.	MoO ₂ (acac) ₂ .PMU (MoC ₁₇ H ₂₉ N ₃ O ₇)	Light green	230	19.85 (19.90)	42.20 (42.25)	5.99 (5.96)	8.67 (8.64)	-	52
4.	MoO ₂ (acac) ₂ .PMTU (MoC ₁₇ H ₂₉ N ₃ O ₆ S)	Light brown	225	19.21 (19.42)	40.85 (40.83)	5.81 (5.83)	8.41 (8.46)	6.41 (6.47)	46
5.	MoO ₂ (acac) ₂ .PyMU (MoC ₁₆ H ₂₇ N ₃ O ₇)	Light green	228	20.44 (20.61)	40.91 (40.97)	5.75 (5.76)	8.95 (8.92)	-	49
6.	MoO ₂ (acac) ₂ .PyMTU (MoC ₁₆ H ₂₇ N ₃ O ₆ S)	Light green	230	19.77 (19.86)	39.56 (39.59)	5.56 (5.51)	8.65 (8.60)	6.59 (6.64)	38

Table 2. Important IR spectral bands (cm⁻¹) and their assignment

Complex	MoO ₂ ²⁺ unit $\nu(\text{O}=\text{Mo}=\text{O})$	Acetylacetonate ion		$\nu(\text{C}=\text{Z})$ Z = O or S	Ligand	
		$\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$	$\nu(\text{C}\cdots\text{C})$		$\nu(\text{C}-\text{N}-\text{C})$	$\nu(\text{C}-\text{O}-\text{C})$
1	943, 908	1641	1522, 1495	1638	1165, 1139	1105
2	946, 907	1642	1521, 1494	1275, 758	1160, 1135	1107
3	945, 908	1641	1518, 1498	1641	1150, 1120	-
4	942, 906	1640	1524, 1490	1280, 762	1160, 1118	-
5	948, 910	1644	1525, 1492	1620	1152, 1125	-
6	945, 907	1642	1522, 1498	1290, 750	1158, 1130	-

Infrared spectra :

Characteristic IR frequencies of the mixed ligand complexes are listed in Table 2. The IR spectra of the complexes exhibit bands characteristic of presence of *cis*-[MoO₂]²⁺ group, coordinated ligands and acetylacetonate anion. The strong band at 1644–1640 cm⁻¹ and the bands in the region 1525–1490 cm⁻¹ can be assigned to $\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$ and $\nu(\text{C}\cdots\text{C})$ stretching vibrations of acetylacetonate anion indicating the presence of acetylacetonate anion in the complexes. The presence of strong bands at 948–942 and 910–906 cm⁻¹ are characteristic of the presence of *cis*-[MoO₂]²⁺ group in these complexes^{28,29}.

Moreover, in the IR spectra of complexes, the absorption bands at 1641–1620 cm⁻¹ assigned to $\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$ stretching vibration of MMU, PMU and PyMU and the bands at 1290–1275 and 762–750 cm⁻¹ assigned to $\nu(\text{C}=\text{S})$ asymmetric and symmetric vibrations in MMTU, PMTU and PyMTU are lowered by 20–30 cm⁻¹ as compared to free ligands indicating Mo–O or Mo–S bonding. The

$\nu(\text{C}-\text{N}-\text{C})$ mode of morpholine, piperidine or pyrrolidine ring around 1165–1150 and 1139–1118 cm⁻¹ are found almost at the same positions in the complexes as in the free ligands indicating the non-involvement of ring nitrogen in coordination to the metal. Thus, these observations suggest the monodentate behaviour of the ligands coordinating to the metal only through carbonyl oxygen or thiocarbonyl sulfur.

Cyclic voltammetry :

The CV graphs of three representative complexes (Figs. 1(a-c)), show an irreversible peak in the cathodic direction at -248 to -366 mV and a quasi-reversible peak at -876 to -1148 mV characteristic of Mo^{VI} → Mo^V and Mo^V → Mo^{IV} reduction. However, in the reverse scan the oxidation of Mo^{IV} → Mo^V skips over and passes to Mo^{VI} state which was confirmed by the *I*_{pa} values of the Mo^{IV}/Mo^{VI} couple (*I*_{pa}/*I*_{pc} ~ 2). The poor chemical stability of Mo^V complexes can be responsible for direct oxidation of Mo^{IV} to Mo^{VI}. Besides this, the cathodic

 Fig. 1a. Cyclic voltammogram of $[\text{MoO}_2(\text{acac})_2 \text{MMU}]$

 Fig. 1b. Cyclic voltammogram of $[\text{MoO}_2(\text{acac})_2 \text{PMTU}]$

 Fig. 1c. Cyclic voltammogram of $[\text{MoO}_2(\text{acac})_2 \text{PyMU}]$

peak potential (E_{pc}) of these mixed ligand complexes is higher than that of $\text{MoO}_2(\text{acac})_2$ complex indicating lower electron accepting ability of mixed ligand complexes. This may be due to the fact that $\text{Mo}^{\text{VI}} \rightarrow \text{Mo}^{\text{IV}}$ reduction process is influenced by coordination number and stereochemistry³². The electrochemical data of some representative complexes is presented in Table 3.

Table 3. Electrochemical data of the complexes

Complex	Peak	Scan rate (mV/s)	E_{pc} (mV)	E_{pa} (mV)	ΔE_p (mV)	I_{pa}/I_{pc} (μA)
$\text{MoO}_2(\text{acac})_2 \text{MMU}$	I	100	-248	-	-	-
	II	100	-876	1195	319	1.97
$\text{MoO}_2(\text{acac})_2 \text{PMTU}$	I	100	-366	-	-	-
	II	100	-943	1114	171	2.0
$\text{MoO}_2(\text{acac})_2 \text{PyMU}$	I	100	-340	-	-	-
	II	100	-1148	1576	428	1.99

Electronic spectra :

The electronic spectra of these mixed ligand complexes show 3-4 high energy absorption bands in 10^{-3} DMSO in the region 384–248 nm (Table 4). The completely resolved band in the region 384–342 nm can be assigned to $\pi\text{-}\pi^*$ transitions of acetylacetonate anions³⁰ whereas the intense band at 365–330 nm can be assigned to transitions from molybdenyl oxygen to an empty molybdenum orbital i.e. $\pi\text{O}_2^- \rightarrow \text{Mo}(\text{dxy})$ LMCT transition³¹. Other bands in the region 318–248 nm can be attributed to intra ligand ($\text{L} \rightarrow \text{L}$) transitions.

Thermal studies :

The TG curves of the complexes were recorded in the temperature range of 35–850 °C. The TG curves of all the complexes are almost similar and weight loss continues till a stable oxide is formed. The TGA/DTA curves of two representative complexes are shown in Figs. 2a and 2b. The decomposition of all the complexes is completed in two steps which is supported by two sharp endothermic peaks in the DTA curves. The first peak is small and corresponds to an initial weight loss of urea or thiourea in the temperature range of 160–200 °C. The second step of decomposition at 570–620 °C can be attributed to the loss of remaining organic part of the ligand and the acetylacetonate anion leading to the formation of stable metal oxide, MoO_2 as on further increasing the temperature no weight loss is observed. However, the poor thermal and chemical stability does not allow one to

Table 4. Electronic and thermal data of complexes

Complex	Electronic data			Thermal data					
	$\pi O_2^- \rightarrow Mo(d_{xy})$	$\pi-\pi^*$ transitions	L \rightarrow L transitions	Dec. temp. (°C)	% wt. loss (obs. (calcd.))	Residue compd.	$-E^*$ kJ mol ⁻¹	Z s ⁻¹	$-\Delta S$ JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹
1	340	370	292	585	73.56 (73.64)	MoO ₂	43.10	2212	180.12
2	355	375	305	592	74.33 (74.48)	MoO ₂	39.40	1881	183.64
3	357	370	290	566	73.28 (73.53)	MoO ₂	46.61	2379	185.12
4	365	384	318	620	74.22 (74.38)	MoO ₂	42.72	2322	186.03
5	330	342	248	570	72.48 (72.74)	MoO ₂	44.13	2305	189.72
6	345	352	291	578	73.44 (73.64)	MoO ₂	43.18	2161	186.16

Fig. 2a. Thermal analysis results of [MoO₂(acac)₂.MMTU].

Fig. 2b. Thermal analysis results of [MoO₂(acac)₂.PMU].

isolate and hence identify the intermediate species formed during decomposition of the complexes.

Coats and Redfern methods have been used for finding the kinetic parameters of the complexes. The fractional weight loss and corresponding $(1 - \alpha)^n$ values have been calculated from the TG curves at different temperature, where 'n' depends upon the reaction model and $\alpha = (W_0 - W_t)/(W_0 - W_f)$. The weighted least square method (LSM) was used for obtaining best linear plots

and kinetic parameters were calculated. The decomposition of the complexes have been observed to follow first order kinetics as is evident for the linear plot of $-\log [1 - \alpha]/T^2$ vs $1/T$. The values of intercept, slope and hence the activation energy (E_a) were obtained from the plots. The value of frequency factor (Z) and entropy of activation (ΔS^*) was calculated from the equations :

$$\text{Intercept} = \log ZR/\beta E_a$$

$$\text{and } \Delta S^* = 2.303 R \log Zh/kT$$

(where k is Boltzman constant, T the peak temperature and β the heating rate).

The thermo-analytical data of the complexes is given in Table 4. On the basis of above studies the following structure is proposed for the complexes.

L = MMU, MMTU, PMU, PMTU, PyMU and PyMTU

L = MMU; X = O and L = MMTU; X = S

Experimental

Morpholine (Fluka), piperidine (SDS), pyrrolidine (Fluka) and acetylacetone (Merck) were purified by distillation after keeping the bases over potassium hydroxide over night. Urea (Merck), thiourea (Ranbaxy), formaldehyde (Qualigens) and ammonium molybdate (Merck) were used as such. The ligands and the complex, $\text{MoO}_2(\text{acac})_2$ were prepared by reported methods^{23,13,14}. Molybdenum analysis was done by reported method³³. Carbon, hydrogen and nitrogen analysis were performed by microanalytical methods. Molar conductivity in DMF (10^{-3} M) at room temperature was measured using Elico Conductivity Bridge, type CM82T and conductivity cell with a cell constant of 0.74. IR spectra of complexes over the region $4000\text{--}400\text{ cm}^{-1}$ were recorded on Bruker FTIR spectrophotometer VECTOR-22 using KBr disc. The electronic spectra of the complexes were recorded using a double beam UV-spectrophotometer type SL164. The cyclic voltammetric behaviour of the complexes was studied in 10^{-3} M DMSO solution using 0.1 mol L^{-1} tetraethylammonium perchlorate as supporting electrolyte on BAS CV 50 W electrochemical analyzer with a scan rate of 100 mV/s using a three electrode system with platinum disc as working electrode, platinum wire as counter electrode and Ag/AgCl as reference electrode. The thermogravimetric analysis (TGA/DTA) of complexes was recorded on DTG 60 thermoanalyser at a heating rate of $20\text{ }^\circ\text{C/min}$.

Preparation of mixed ligand complexes :

To 20 ml ethanolic solution of 3.26 g (0.01 mol) of $[\text{MoO}_2(\text{acac})_2]$ was added an equimolar ethanolic solution of the corresponding ligand (20 ml) dropwise with constant stirring. The resulting solution was refluxed on a water bath for 20–30 min. The coloured precipitates formed on cooling down the solution to room temperature were filtered, washed with ethanol and dried in a vacuum desiccator.

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